

A model for taking pleasant/unpleasant brain waves of Coca Cola customers by using the physics and mobile technology

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Abstract: Coca Cola as the famous brand should think about very new technology to take idea of customers, otherwise, confront many hard economical problems and other companies take its place. In this research, using the concepts in physics, we propose a model which helps the Coca Cola to analyse brain waves of customers. In this method, by opening a bottle, differences between temperatures and pressures inside and outside it cause to the emergence of some electrical currents. These currents reach to mouth, taste cells and their related nerve systems and some electrons even turn over the head and act like the electrodes of EEG. Any pleasant or unpleasant signal within the nerve systems could be taken by these electrons and transmitted to the nearest mobile receiver. Then, mobile cells could put these information on the wireless waves and send to towers. Coca Cola operators could take information from towers and analyze data.

Keywords: Coca Cola, Brain Waves, Customers, Mobile technology

I. Introduction

One of famous carbonated soft drinks in the world is producing by the Coca Cola company [1-3]. The real formula of Coca Cola is a trade secret; however, many reported recipes and experimental results about its components and elements have been published [4-6]. The drink's name refers to two of its original ingredients: coca leaves and kola nuts (a source of caffeine). Both of these matters have many medical applications. For example, coca could act as a mild stimulant and suppresses hunger, thirst, pain and fatigue [7]. Or kola nuts may be useful for aiding digestion when ground and mixed with honey, and may be used as a remedy for coughs [8]. Also, Coca Cola drink may contain Carbonated water, Caffeine, Phosphoric acid, Sodium and Sugar [9,10].

Now, the question arises that how this company could take idea of customers for its products. Maybe, people in one country or region like a taste but people in other country hate it. These

differences between people could become problematic and endanger the future of the company. Specially, there are serious competitor for this brand which try to take its place [11,12]. We propose a model which uses of physics and mobile technology for taking real idea of customers. In our model, by opening the door of a bottle, a signal is emerged, take taste cortex information of customer and goes towards a cell phone. This signal is sending to mobile tower and then it could be analyzed by an analyzer in Coca Cola company.

The outline of paper is as follows: In section II, we describe the method for imaging the idea of customers by using their EEG waves. In section III, we bring some observations. The last section is devoted to conclusion.

II. Method. A model for taking pleasant/non-pleasant idea of customers for Coca Cola by analysing their brain waves

For a famous brand like Coca Cola, it is very main to know idea of customers. Because, any small mistake in choosing taste could destroy the validity of company and cause to many economical problems. Specially, in conditions that there are strong competitors that like to take the place of Coca Cola (See Figure 1. A). Also, people in different regions give different ideas and votes to this brand (See Figure 1.B). This is because that each culture may like special tastes and hate some other tastes. Thus, it is needed to know idea of people in different regions. However, it is very hard to take idea by using traditional methodes like contacting by phones. Physics may help us to analyse thoughts faster.

To make an analyzer system, we can use of below devices:

Bottles, Coca Cola bubbles, Coca Cola ions or charges, Faces and brains, Mobile cell phones, Towers, Coca Cola Analyzer

In an analyzer system:

First, a bottle is opened and many bubbles come from it. Temperatures and pressures inside and outside the bottle are different. This difference in temperatures provides an energy to separate electrons from some molecules and bubbles and produce an electrical current (See Figure 2).

If we suppose that T1 is temperature within a bottle and T2 is temperature around the bottle, emitted energy could be:

$$E = k (T1 - T2)$$

This energy could force the bubbles to disappear and two types of electrons with opposite spins are emerged (See Figure 3).

These electrons move towards mouth and turn around the head and nerve system of customer. They could take information from taste cortex and act like the EEG waves. Within the mouth and around the taste cells, there are some neurons and receptors which connect cells to nerve system and brain. Electrical currents could interact with charges within or around neurons and take nerve messages. If we establish a soft ware on mobiles, it gives this possibility to them that take these electrons and send some signals to towers. Although, even without these softwares, a mobile could send information through wireless waves. Then, towers could give these signals to Coca Cola analyzors. By analysing these signals, one can understand that customers like a taste or hate it (See Figure 4).

A. Coca Cola in competition with other drinks

B. Coca Cola distributions in different regions

Figure 1. A. Coca Cola in competition with other drinks. B. Coca Cola market distribution different regions [9-12].

Figure 2. Emergence of electronic currents during evaporation of gases from Coca Cola drink

Figure 3. Differences between temperatures and pressures inside and outside of a bottle cause to the emergence of electrons

Figure 4. Emerged electrons between a Coca Cola bottle and mouth and head could active a soft ware on a mobile and transmit EEG waves towards towers and then towards Coca Cola analyzors.

III. Some observations of Coca Cola ions and their effects on mobile phones

A Coca Cola bottle has different molecules which some of them are unknown. We put a sample of this drink under a 1000x microscope. We observed that some ionic circles are formed around some molecules (See Figure 5). Under some thermodynamics or electronically conditions, shape, size and color of rings change (See Figure 6). This means that this drink has many free ions and charges or electrons which are very sensitive to any change in medium. Thus, using these charges, we can take information from different parts of brain like the taste cortex. From other side, many micro bubbles could be observed because, .within liquid of this drink. These bubbles could be signature of ions. parallel electrons repel each other and form needed empty spaces for producing bubbles (See Figure 7).

To consider effects of charges, ions and electrons within Coca Cola drink on a mobile phone, we can use of some softwares. Although, for real analyze, company should design its special soft wares. However, we provide some observations that show model works. To this aim, we use of card sound. Because, it could be connected to currents outside the mobile and acts as the analyzer of electrons. Without Coca Cola, we have normal frequencies and waves (See Figure 8). However, if we connect two mobiles by whatsapp or phone waves and open a bottle of Coca Cola, we could see significant changes in signals (See Figure 9). Any pleasant and unpleasant taste not only has a direct effect on electrons within or around mouth but also could change sound waves so. Because, for example, unpleasant taste affect taste cells and also neurons around them. These informations move along nerve system and reach to the brain. Unpleasant taste causes to confusing and vibration of customer sound and we can see these vibrations on the scope. However, it is recommended that Coca Cola Company invent its special softwares and send it to all cell phones by the help of mobile companies.

Figure 5. The effect of ions and charges within Coca Cola on the size of molecules under 1000x microscope

Figure 6. A sudden change in shape of molecules by changes of ions and charges within Cica Cola under 1000x microscope

Figure 7. Emergence of micro bubbles and electrons within a bottle of Coca Cola under microscope

Figure 8. Electrical currents which are measured by mobile sound card before Coca Cola vaborayion.

Figure 9. Analyzing effects of Coca Cola drink on electronic currents around the mouth by connecting two mobiles

Conclusion

All famous companies need to know idea of customers, otherwise, they lose their place and bear many expenses. Old methods for taking customer ideas by phone contacts or mail couldn't work now. Because, a company like the Coca Cola needs to know idea of customers in each time. We suggested a model which Coca Cola could take idea of customers by analysing their brain waves. In this model, motions of bubbles and gases between a bottle and a mouth produce electrical currents. These electrons interact with electrons and charges within neurons around taste cells and nerve system and take their information. Then, these informations are taken by nearest cell phones and transmitted to nearest towers through wireless waves. Towers separate these waves and send to Coca Cola Analyzers. Finally, analyzers consider signals and understand that a customer like a taste or hate it.

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